

THE ROLE OF FERGHANA VALLEY WOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract:

In this article, the activities of women in the socio-economic and cultural spheres of Uzbekistan during the years of independence are highlighted on the example of the Fergana Valley (Andijan, Namangan, Fergana regions). The work of women who are mature specialists in their profession, dedicated to their work and received recognition is revealed.

Key words: Domestic market, private enterprise, workforce, economic development, jobs, employment, country of youth, entrepreneurship.

INTRODUCTION

Social, economic and cultural processes play an important role in the development of society. The historical analysis of these processes and the ability to adequately assess the role of women in them serve as the basis for raising the social, economic and cultural life of New Uzbekistan to new levels. These processes are one of the most important and urgent issues facing the history and historians of Uzbekistan. Therefore, it is necessary to deeply study the directions of development of Uzbekistan in the social, economic and cultural spheres, and first of all, to deeply analyze the contribution and contribution of women in these processes. Studying these processes, analyzing the development characteristics of these industries and the rational use of labor resources, making suggestions in this regard is an urgent issue and is one of the needs of today.

Women have made a great contribution to Uzbekistan's rightful place in history. The bravery of Tomaris in the history of the ancient world, the entrepreneurship of Mrs. Saraymulk, who fully justified the name Bibikhanim in the Middle Ages, and the construction of buildings, Nodirabegim during the Khanate period, the magic of the pen of the Uvaisis, the artistic Tamarakhanim (1906-1991) and Mukarram Turgunboyeva (1913 -1978), sniper Zebo Ganiyeva (1923-2010), our women like Fatima Kasimova, a tolerant woman from Samarkand, can be real examples for all times.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In 1991, when the Uzbek people achieved their age-old dream, fundamental changes began to progress in all areas. In such a responsible period, the women of Ferghana Valley also contributed significantly to the social, economic and cultural development of Uzbekistan. It is clear that carrying out social or cultural reforms in the country goes back to the material aspect. So, first of all, it was necessary to develop the country economically, create new jobs and reduce unemployment. An important feature of Uzbekistan is the high rate of population growth. In 1990-1996, the population of the country increased by 13.3 percent. The average annual growth rate of the population was 2.0 percent in 1996, or the population increased by 450,000 people in one year. Year by year, the need to create new jobs was increasing.

RESULTS

Entrepreneurship is an important factor in developing the economy of our country, providing employment, and raising the standard of living of the population. Masudakhan Sodikova, who was born in Namangan district of Namangan region and is engaged in business activities in Torakorgan district, who aims to provide employment to the women of Namangan region, is one of the successful entrepreneurs. Masudakhan Sodikova started her business in 1991. It created 100 jobs in Yortepa neighborhood. Later, he founded the private enterprise "Dilrabo SDA", using the opportunities wisely. The production of knitwear products has been launched at this enterprise. The manufactured products were put on sale in special stores of the enterprise in the cities of Toraqorgan, Namangan and Andijan. The volume of work increased year by year, while the domestic market was secured, the products began to be exported abroad. 90% of the company's employees are women. The system of hot food and transport was introduced to the workers.

In Eastern nations, the family is considered a sacred place. It's not for nothing, of course. From the first years of independence, family and women's issues were considered at the level of state policy. Taking into account that the strength of the state is inextricably linked to the strength of its families, 1998 was declared the "Year of the Family" in our country. In this regard, the Republican "Family" scientific-practical center was established. Being one of the first, a branch of this center was also established in Namangan region. The management of this new system was entrusted to Dilbar Zohidova, one of the passionate women of the region. In this field, practical work was carried out on issues such as finding solutions to family problems and preventing family disputes. In 2000, Dilbar Zohidova was appointed head of the Namangan Region branch of the "For a Healthy Generation" fund. The foundation under the leadership of Dilbar Zokhidova has done many good things. In particular, he sponsored the "Chortoq" children's hospital in the region, the "Mother and Child" screening centers, and the "Children's Garden and Wellness Center" included in the State program was established in Davlatabad. Since 2002, Dilbar Zokhidova, who is used to being active, started doing business. Under his leadership, the private enterprise "Oybarshah" was launched. Due to her hard work, Dilbar Zohidova was awarded with the "Badge of Independence", the "Sign of Honor" order, the "For Passionate Work" medal, and the "Excellence of Public Education of Uzbekistan" badge.

DISCUSSION

The farmer Patilakhan Ergasheva, who was awarded the title of "Hero of Uzbekistan" for his effective work on the development of Uzbekistan, and the skilled pedagogue Manzurakhan Madaliyeva are famous not only in the Fergana Valley, but throughout Uzbekistan. The women of Ferghana Valley are responsible for both family and profession, and can put everything in place. Patilakhan Ergasheva, the founder of the "Patilakhon" farm in Buvayda district, who worked with boundless zeal for work, is one of the women who made a great contribution to the development of cotton farming and cotton growing. Patilakhan Ergasheva, who first led the cocooning and then the cotton-growing brigades, gained respect among the people with his tireless work. In the early years of independence, cotton became important in the economy of our country as white gold. Due to the trust in his work and responsibility, the "Fergana-3" seed was tested for the first time in his brigade. The hard work of a hardworking person has yielded more results than expected. During her career, the Mirishkor woman from Buvaida was able to create a unique school in the development of cotton growing, which is the

main branch of agriculture. Effectively using her many years of experience, this female farmer achieved high results. Just one example, in 2019, they grew Namangan-77 cotton on 30 hectares of land, harvested more than 125 tons, and increased the annual contract plan by 127 percent. It is impossible not to acknowledge the efforts of our selfless women like Motabarkhan Rakhimova, Matluba Otajonova, and Fatima Jorayeva as members of this farm in achieving such productivity. Patilakhan Ergasheva's services to the country were duly appreciated, in 2010 she was awarded the title of "Hero of Uzbekistan".

Poets and writers such as Saida Zunnunova, Enakhon Siddikova, Berta Davidova, Halima Nosirova, Gavhar Rahimova, Munojot Yolchiyeva, Hurriyat Isroilova, Yorkinoy Hotamova, who made an incomparable contribution to the development of Uzbek culture, art and literature of the Fergana Valley. It is the cradle of artists such as Gulsanam Mamazoitova, Zulayho Boyhonova, Mehri Abdullayeva. The spiritual life of the population is constantly connected with art. The people of Ferghana Valley have made poems, melodies and songs a part of their life.

Undoubtedly, Uzbekistan can be called "the country of youth". The reason is that more than half of the population of Uzbekistan is made up of young people, and in turn, the youth of our country act as active participants, not spectators, in the development of Uzbekistan. In this regard, a number of young people of the Fergana Valley, such as Mehrinoz Abbasova, winner of the state award named after Zulfia, Alimakhon Tojiboyeva, Malika Egamberdiyeva, winner of the "Nihol" award, can serve as an example for everyone. Although they are young, they make good use of the opportunities created, enrich the youth page of their lives meaningfully and encourage the rest of their peers to do the same.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that while analyzing the activities of women of Fergana region in the development of Uzbekistan in various fields, we can see the efforts of representatives of three generations in this process. The reason is that the youth of the younger generation, the representatives of the middle generation who have already become mature specialists in their field, and our elders, who are leading students with their life experiences and knowledge, are not indifferent to the fate of the homeland. They contribute to the future of this country. Women account for 49.7% of the population of Uzbekistan and 45% of labor resources. For this reason, the issues of social life and development in all spheres of Uzbekistan are related to women. Women are also actively participating in the successful implementation of the reforms, which are expanding in size and scope. Like many countries, economic processes play an important role in the development of Uzbekistan. Analyzing these processes historically and being able to adequately assess the role of women in them will serve as a basis for the economic and social life of New Uzbekistan to rise to new levels. These processes are one of the most important and urgent issues facing the history and historians of Uzbekistan. Also, it is necessary to thoroughly study the directions of development of Uzbekistan in the economic and social spheres, first of all, to analyze deeply the share and contribution of women in these processes. Studying these processes, analyzing the development characteristics of these industries and the issues of rational use of labor resources, making suggestions in this regard is an urgent issue and is considered one of the needs of today.

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